

REQUIREMENTS FOR THE MUSIC TEACHER IN IMPROVING MUSIC LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the duties and requirements of a music teacher in shaping and improving music education lessons.

Key words: Educational system, music culture, pedagogical skill, methodology, creative activity.

Introduction.

In the current period, it is extremely necessary to search for effective forms and methods of preparing the young generation, who are our future, for life based on the latest achievements of science and culture. According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the further improvement and efficiency of the "Spirituality and Enlightenment" public center, the development of high moral qualities in the society, the formation of national ideology, the development of people with a rich cultural education in the spirit of loyalty to our historical traditions, universal values, love of country, independence ideas is the decisive factor of all the reforms implemented in our country.

Based on the principles of democratization of education, individualization, consideration of regional characteristics, a new teaching concept was developed for all academic subjects, including music lessons. These circumstances were also reflected in the reworked programs from the point of view of the priority of national music.

Aesthetic education is the formation and development of feelings, understanding and thirst for beauty, as well as striving to live and create based on the laws of beauty, which are an integral part of personal education.

It is necessary to structure the aesthetic education of students during the years and at different stages. The form, purpose, content, originality of the training from the pedagogical point of view, as well as work plans should be differentiated according to the age and capabilities of the children, taking into account the logic of science.

It is necessary to direct the students to the aesthetic values that have an impact on the environment. Literature rich in national traditions, visual arts, especially eastern miniature art, sculpture, music and other types of art (theatre, circus, etc.), people's past and present way of life, place of residence, clothing, work weapons.

Requirements for music lessons and music teachers in improving music lessons:

The introduction of the state standard of music education made it possible to use our national musical heritage and get acquainted with the art and culture of regional oases, where local folk traditions are expressed. Also, according to its structure and content, the educational standard reflects the balance of interests and means of the state, region, school, and a new program for classes was created taking into account the personality of the student, his aspirations, abilities and interests. Based on the program, textbooks, methodological

manuals, recommendations are being created. During the seven-year period of music education, the main goal is to educate students to become well-rounded people who can feel beauty, look at music with love and envy, and inherit our national musical heritage. Based on the new program, in order to conduct the music lesson at a high quality, pedagogical and methodical level, he must be a teacher, a creator, a person who loves his profession and students, a good musician, who has thoroughly mastered methodology and pedagogy. need

Also, the Uzbek people must follow and study the history of our musical heritage and current requirements. Because the main goal of music education at school is to develop musical culture in students. A music teacher should be able to choose topics for classes, use visual aids and technical tools in planning, and teach using new pedagogical and information technologies. In the music lesson, it is necessary to realize the developmental, educational and educational tasks of achieving mutual logical unity based on the principle of transition of musical activities from simple to complex.

In specialized music schools, music culture lessons are of great importance, along with all the subjects taught at the school, in the education of students to become mature in all aspects. Music expresses human feelings, dreams and desires in its own artistic language and has an active influence on emotions.

The main goal of music culture classes is to arouse interest in music and form musical imagination in students, to consciously perceive music as an art. As a result, children have the basic principles of observing music. To achieve this goal, the following tasks are performed:

Development of students' musical abilities, development of music (listening) perception skills, singing skills development, moral-aesthetic education through the artistic-ideal content of music.

Requirements for professional training of a music teacher:

Lessons of modern music culture can be considered an artistic-pedagogical work, because the teacher creates it based on his individual creativity and experience. The composition and dramaturgy of the lesson, its artistic-pedagogical idea, goals and tasks, forms, methodological methods and technologies are also used to increase students' interest in music, to inculcate in them the spiritual theme of musical art and culture, modern musical-creative understanding of the activity - all this belongs to the creative sphere of the teacher.

The main goal of music education in a specialized music school is to educate students ideologically, emotionally and morally, to influence the development of their general culture by forming a musical culture in them. That is why the educational system includes music education as an important factor in the development of the young generation. In particular, playing music is an activity of artistic cognition: it forms ideological beliefs, educates morals, determines the psychological purpose of interests and thinking in a person, creates, organizes and unites social mood, educates social activity, art develops the ability to perceive, feel and understand music, develops aesthetic and musical taste, strengthens mental maturity, creative activity, thinking, individuality of students, expands the range of thoughts, develops the necessary musical knowledge, skills and abilities helps to solve the problem of free time.

Therefore, it can be said that the subject of "Music" in school is a way to educate and improve students not only morally and aesthetically, but in all aspects.

The activity of a music teacher is not limited to conducting music lessons, his task is to organize music circles, music lectures and clubs, prepare and conduct music evenings and competitions, supervise school amateurs, organize cultural marches to the Philharmonic,

music theater activities such as setting up work are also included. This includes teaching music to adults: parents, teachers, and leaders.

In order for a music teacher to successfully carry out his professional activity, he must perform all the tasks related to this activity, and these, in our opinion, include the following:

Determining all parts of the education-training process: organizational-meaningful work (choosing the content of music education and training);

Communication works - the teacher's communication with students in the process of education, as well as mutual cooperation with the team of school pedagogues, parents and the public.

Organizational activities related to the implementation of the plan of the educational process (organization of one's statement, behavior and activities of students, various forms of the educational process).

Developmental work consists of foreseeing the growth of each student and the improvement of the student team, defining and consistently implementing the tasks of general and special (musical) development of boys and girls.

Guiding works on the formation of a certain system of socially significant values in students: the formation of ideas and values, the formation of needs, interests, tastes, the reasons for activity and behavior, worldview and feeling of the world.

Research works on the study of pedagogical processes and phenomena. Pedagogical activity requires the following from the teacher:

- to study the dynamics of students' abilities, interest in music, musical knowledge, and their acquisition of performing skills and qualifications;
- to learn teaching methods, to determine effective methods and the conditions of their successful application;
- to study methodological manuals and developments (their critical assessment);
- to analyze positive and negative experiences of oneself and other teachers; generalize effective methods and forms of work and use them in one's practice;
- regular pedagogical observations and experiments.

Performing works: it consists in showing an artistic effect on students, school teams, parents, and the public with one's performance art. These tasks require not only the acquisition of performance skills in various musical activities (singing, conducting, playing instruments, ensemble), but also the ability to manage the performance activities of students.

Musical-educational works consisting of promotion of musical-aesthetic knowledge, advanced events of past and present music culture, activation of artistic amateurism as the most important factor of public education and so on. These are absorbed into the entire professional and social activities of the music teacher and are based on understanding the art of music as a means of ideologically influencing the mind and emotions of a person, forming political, moral and aesthetic views in it.

A music teacher must love his subject (music), approach it enthusiastically, love people, be interested in teaching and educating with the tools of musical art. Thus, the system of music teacher's knowledge is made up of social-political-psychological-pedagogical and special knowledge.

Socio-political knowledge is the foundation of the teacher's outlook, the methodological base of professional and special knowledge.

Special knowledge includes the history and theory of general music pedagogy, methods of teaching piano playing, conducting, and singing. For a pedagogue of any specialty, special abilities are also necessary, without which it is impossible to carry out appropriate pedagogical activities.

Musical skills are very important for a music teacher. The set of such abilities is quite wide and complex, which will be discussed later. But it should be noted that having musical abilities is a mandatory condition for musical activity and for managing this activity in any framework of music education and education.

When the teacher prepares the music lesson plan, he determines the purpose, task, topic, type and forms of teaching, music activities and the necessary methods, technologies and methods for instilling them in the students, and then creates the scenario of the lesson. The lesson is organized in a general scheme. Each type of activity: listening to music, singing as a team, musical literacy, rhythmic movements, accompanying a musical instrument, games - should be connected and integrated. Various technologies, tools, methods and ways are used for active participation of students in the lesson.

A music teacher meets with students almost every day, answers questions, approves their good work, evaluates their knowledge, and reprimands them for their bad behavior. Of course, there are signs of relativity and subjectivity in the music teacher's thoughts and opinions. He may not be able to treat everyone exactly the same. But everyone needs to be convinced that he is a fair person, who strives to do good, and is fair to all students. There should not be an impression that there are students who like or dislike the music teacher in the class.

Conclusion.

So, reputation is a necessary feature for teaching. Reputation is an influence recognized by many, acquired due to a person's deep knowledge, high moral qualities, life experience, active participation in scientific research and public affairs.

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